

Secrets of the Rapid Growth of the Chinese Economy from the Perspectives of Government, Party, Statesmen and Political Behavioral Economics

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This article aims to conduct an in-depth exploration of the inherent mysteries behind the rapid development of China's economy under the leadership of the Communist Party of China and the government, which has enabled it to rank second in the world. It focuses on analyzing from the perspectives of government behavioral economics, party behavioral economics, politician behavioral economics, and political behavioral economics. The Communist Party of China guides the direction of economic development through scientific strategic planning, continuous institutional innovation, and powerful social mobilization. On the other hand, the government takes active measures in multiple aspects, such as macroeconomic regulation and control, infrastructure construction, and optimization of the business environment, and local governments also compete and cooperate in an orderly manner. In the political realm, the foundation of the political system has been firmly established to safeguard the long-term development of the economy. From the perspective of politician behavioral economics, focusing on the eras of Mao Zedong, Zhou Enlai, Deng Xiaoping, and Xi Jinping, this article deeply analyzes the profound impacts of Chinese politicians' strategic decisions and policy implementations on economic development in different periods. It explores the internal logic and driving forces that have enabled China's economy to gradually rise from a backward position to become the second largest in the world, revealing economic wisdom and the "code" of development that meets the needs of the times under the leadership of politicians, and providing a unique interpretation for understanding the miracle of China's economic growth. Meanwhile, it interprets that institutional economics, in the context of Chinese characteristics, takes the forms of government, party, statesmen and political behavioral economics. These factors are intertwined and work in synergy, jointly promoting the rapid take-off of China's economy.

Keywords: political party behavior economy · politician behavior economy · government behavioral economy · political behavior economy · political party behavior economics · politician or statesman or statesmen behavior economics · government behavior economics · political behavior economics · institutional economics · traffic light coalition · Mao Zedong era · Deng Xiaoping era · Xi Jinping era · economic growth · economic policy · strategy · macroeconomic regulation · opening-up · reform

1. Introduction

China's economy has achieved an astonishing leap in the past few decades, rapidly rising from a relatively backward economy to become the world's second largest economy. This remarkable achievement has attracted widespread attention and in-depth research around the world.

The Western academic community has been constantly debating the secret behind China's remarkable economic achievements. Perhaps they believe that there is currently no theory or approach that fits Western academic logic and is suitable for interpreting China's remarkable economic achievements. However, the author believes that institutional economics theory in today's world has hindered the mainstream economic community in the world from understanding China's great economic success. Because institutional economics in today's world has not clearly pointed out that a country's institutional economy itself originates from the economic behavior of political parties, politicians, politics, and government. This institutional economics itself derives from the economics of political party behavior, politician behavior, political behavior, and government behavior. Without politicians, political parties, politics and government, the economic systems of Western countries today would have no roots. It can be seen from the author's other three articles on political party behavior economics that the rules of economic operation related to institutional economy in Germany and the United States are also basically determined by the economic behavior of political parties, politicians, politics and government. A large number of facts have already formed historical bases.

In the past four years, the author of this article has mentioned that the development of government behavioral finance, party behavioral finance, party behavioral economy, government behavioral economy, enterprise behavioral economy, tourism behavioral economy, rural behavioral economy and market economy with Chinese characteristics is the secret behind China's economic take-off. Among many analytical perspectives, the author believes that government behavioral economics, party behavioral economics, politician behavioral economics, and political behavioral economics provide unique and profound dimensions for the public to understand this phenomenon. Delving deeply into the internal logic and mechanisms therein will not only help reveal the secrets of China's economic growth, but also have extremely important reference significance for the theory and practice of global economic development.

2. Party Behavioral Economics: The Leading Role of the Communist Party of China

2.1. Forward-looking Strategic Planning

The Communist Party of China has always been planning the blueprint for economic development with a far-sighted strategic vision. The strategy of "socialist industrialization and socialist transformation of the ownership of the means of production" in the early days of the founding of the People's Republic of China rapidly promoted the process of socialist industrialization and completed the socialist transformation of ownership of the means of production, laying a solid foundation for the socialist economic system. Subsequently, the system of "Five-Year Plans" is like a

series of closely connected economic development ladders, which methodically guides the allocation of resources to key industries and crucial fields. For example, the First Five-Year Plan focused on developing heavy industries and initially established the national industrialization system. After the reform and opening up, multiple Five-Year Plans have adapted to the changes in domestic and international situations in a timely manner, promoting the transformation of the economy from a planned economy to a market economy and shifting the focus from emphasizing quantitative growth to pursuing quality improvement. Since the 18th National Congress of the Communist Party of China, the new development concepts of "innovation, coordination, green development, opening up, and sharing" have pointed out the direction for high-quality economic development in the new era, ensuring that economic development is interconnected at various stages under the guidance of long-term goals and avoiding the blindness and short-sightedness of development.

2.2. Innovative institutional changes

Institutional innovation is the key magic weapon for the Communist Party of China in leading economic construction. From breaking the shackles of the traditional planned economic system and embarking on the great journey of reforming the market economic system to establishing the basic economic system in which public ownership is dominant and diverse forms of ownership develop together, this series of changes has greatly unleashed economic vitality. In rural areas, the implementation of the household contract responsibility system has endowed farmers with the autonomy in land management, stimulated the production enthusiasm of the vast number of farmers, and liberated rural productive forces. In urban areas, the reform of state-owned enterprises has gradually promoted the establishment of the modern enterprise system, improving the market competitiveness and operational efficiency of enterprises. In addition, institutional innovations in fields such as finance, fiscal and taxation, and foreign trade, such as the reform of the exchange rate system, the reform of the tax sharing system, and the adjustment of the foreign trade system after joining the World Trade Organization, have all effectively promoted the optimal allocation of resources, reduced transaction costs, enabled the Chinese economy to better integrate into the global economic system, and created a favorable institutional environment for economic growth.

2.3. Strong social mobilization and integration capacity

The Communist Party of China possesses outstanding social mobilization and integration capabilities and can rally the strength of the whole society to engage in economic construction. Through the Party organization network covering the whole country and in-depth publicity and education work at the grassroots level, the Party's economic development strategies and policy guidelines have been widely disseminated and deeply rooted in people's hearts. Although the "Great Leap Forward" campaign during the socialist construction period had some mistakes, it also reflected the attempt to mobilize the masses on a large scale to participate in economic construction at that time. After the reform and opening up, township and village enterprises sprang up like mushrooms, which was a testament to the active entrepreneurship of the vast number of farmers under the call of the Party's policies.

At the same time, the Party pays attention to coordinating the interest relations among all parties. By implementing regional coordinated development strategies, such as Western Development, the Rise of Central China, and the Revitalization of Northeast China, it has narrowed the regional development gap, promoted balanced regional development, reduced possible social contradictions caused by the widening gap between the rich and the poor, and provided a harmonious and stable social environment for sustained and stable growth of the economy. In the face of major natural disasters and global economic crises, the Party can quickly mobilize the strength of the whole country to unite as one and overcome difficulties together. For example, during the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic, while effectively controlling the epidemic, it actively promoted the resumption of work and production, minimizing the impact of the pandemic on the economy to the greatest extent, demonstrating the important supporting role of strong social mobilization and crisis response capabilities in the stable development of the economy.

3. Government Behavioral Economics: The Core Driving Role of the Chinese Central Government

3.1. An effective macroeconomic regulation and control system

The Chinese central government has established a sophisticated and flexible macroeconomic regulation and control system, comprehensively utilizing tools such as fiscal policies, monetary policies, and industrial policies to precisely regulate economic operations. When the economy is under downward pressure, proactive fiscal policies, such as increasing government investment and implementing large-scale tax cuts and fee reductions, are put into effect. For example, after the outbreak of the 2008 global financial crisis, the Chinese government launched a "4 trillion yuan" investment plan, with key investments in areas such as infrastructure construction and affordable housing. This not only directly drove the recovery and development of numerous industries such as steel, cement, and construction machinery, but also created a large number of job opportunities, effectively stabilizing expectations for economic growth.

In terms of monetary policy, by adjusting interest rates and the money supply in a timely manner, it influences the investment and consumption decisions of enterprises and residents. For instance, the reserve requirement ratio and benchmark deposit and loan interest rates have been lowered several times to increase market liquidity, reduce enterprise financing costs, and stimulate enterprise investment and household consumption. Industrial policies focus on guiding the adjustment and upgrading of the industrial structure, providing support for emerging industries and phasing out backward production capacities. For example, emerging fields such as the new energy vehicle and photovoltaic industries have been given financial subsidies, tax incentives, and scientific research support to promote their rapid development. For traditional industries like steel and coal, policies to resolve overcapacity have been implemented to promote industrial technological upgrading and green transformation, ensuring that the economy operates smoothly and healthily within a reasonable range and realizes structural optimization.

3.2. Massive investment in infrastructure construction

The government attaches great importance to the fundamental and leading roles of infrastructure construction in economic development and continuously invests huge amounts of funds in infrastructure fields such as transportation, communications, and energy.

In terms of transportation infrastructure, the large-scale construction of the expressway network and high-speed railway network has achieved remarkable results worldwide. China's high-speed railway, with its advantages of high speed, high safety, and long operating mileage, has become a national calling card. It has not only greatly shortened the time and space distances between cities, promoted the flow of people, materials and information among regions, reduced logistics costs, and improved the efficiency of economic operations, but also driven the rapid development of related industries such as high-speed railway equipment manufacturing, engineering construction, and technological research and development, forming a complete high-speed railway industrial chain and creating huge economic benefits and job opportunities.

In the field of communications, from catching up in the 2G and 3G eras, running side by side in the 4G era, to leading in the 5G era, the Chinese government has vigorously supported the construction of communication infrastructure and the innovation of communication technology research and development, promoting the in-depth integration of digital technologies such as the Internet, big data, and artificial intelligence with the real economy and giving birth to a series of emerging business forms and business models such as e-commerce, digital finance, and intelligent manufacturing, laying a solid foundation for the vigorous development of the digital economy and enabling China to occupy a favorable position in the global digital economy competition.

In the construction of energy infrastructure, continuous efforts have been made to strengthen the construction of energy supply networks such as electricity, oil and gas as well as energy reserve facilities, ensuring the energy needs of industrial production and residents' lives. Meanwhile, the development and utilization of new and renewable energy sources have been actively promoted to optimize and upgrade the energy structure, improve energy utilization efficiency and the level of energy security, and provide stable and reliable energy support for the sustainable development of the economy.

3.3. Continuous measures to optimize the business environment

The Chinese government is actively committed to optimizing and improving the business environment, continuously deepening the reform of the administrative examination and approval system, simplifying work procedures, and improving administrative efficiency. Through the implementation of the reform of "streamlining administration, delegating power, and improving regulation and services", a large number of administrative examination and approval items have been cut, and market access restrictions have been relaxed. For example, in the reform of the commercial system, initiatives such as "integrating multiple certificates into one" and "separating permits from business licenses" have been implemented, greatly reducing the start-up costs and time costs of enterprises and stimulating the vitality of market entities.

The protection of intellectual property rights has been strengthened, and intellectual property laws and regulations and law enforcement mechanisms have been improved to encourage enterprises to increase their investment in research and development and technological innovation, improve their core competitiveness, and create a good social atmosphere that respects knowledge and encourages innovation. A sound market supervision system has been established and improved, shifting from the traditional focus on pre-approval to focus on supervision during and after the event, strengthening the maintenance of market order, cracking down on unfair competition, monopoly behaviors, and various illegal and irregular activities, and ensuring a fair and competitive market environment.

The government has also actively built various public service platforms, such as science and technology service platforms and financing service platforms for small and medium-sized enterprises, to provide enterprises with all-round services such as technological research and development support, personnel training, information consultation, and financing guarantees, helping enterprises solve technical, financial, and personnel problems encountered in the development process, promoting the healthy growth and expansion of enterprises, attracting a large number of domestic and foreign enterprises to invest and start businesses, making the Chinese market one of the most attractive investment destinations in the world, and injecting a steady stream of vitality into economic growth.

4. Government Behavioral Economics: The Unique Roles and Functions of Local Governments

4.1. Competition and Incentives among Local Governments

Under the performance assessment orientation centered on economic construction, a positive competitive situation has emerged among local governments. This competition is mainly manifested in several aspects. First, in terms of attracting investment, local governments have introduced preferential policies one after another to attract domestic and foreign investment, including measures such as land incentives, tax reductions and exemptions, and financial subsidies, striving to create a favourable investment environment and attract high-quality enterprises and projects to settle in their local areas. For example, some cities in coastal areas have attracted a large number of foreign-funded enterprises to settle in by building modern industrial parks and providing one-stop services, thus forming export-oriented economic industrial clusters.

Second, in terms of industrial development competition, local governments actively cultivate local characteristic industries, increase support for emerging industries, and promote the transformation and upgrading of traditional industries. For example, some local governments support the development of high-tech enterprises by setting up industrial guidance funds to promote the optimization of local industrial structures and the enhancement of their competitiveness.

Third, in terms of infrastructure construction competition, in order to enhance regional attractiveness and competitiveness, local governments have increased their investment in infrastructure construction such as transportation, communications and

energy, and improved the local hardware environment. To some extent, this kind of competition among local governments has promoted the optimal allocation of resources and the improvement of economic efficiency, stimulated the vitality and creativity of local development, promoted the formation and development of local characteristic economies, and formed a good situation where all regions are vying with each other for development throughout the country.

4.2. Regional cooperation and coordinated development

As economic development has entered a new stage, local governments have gradually realized the importance of regional cooperation and are actively promoting coordinated regional development. The regional integration strategy has become an important carrier for cooperation among local governments, such as the coordinated development of the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region, the integration of the Yangtze River Delta, and the construction of the Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area. In the coordinated development of the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region, Beijing has transferred some industrial, educational and medical resources to Tianjin and Hebei by relieving its non-capital functions. Tianjin has given play to its advantages in ports and manufacturing, and Hebei has undertaken the functions of resource bearing and industrial undertaking. The three regions have carried out in-depth cooperation in aspects such as transportation integration, ecological environment protection, and industrial collaborative innovation, achieving complementary advantages, resource sharing, and coordinated development, and enhancing the comprehensive competitiveness of the entire Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region.

The integration of the Yangtze River Delta has strengthened the division of labor and cooperation between Shanghai and its surrounding cities, forming a multi-level urban system and industrial cluster with Shanghai as the core and cities such as Nanjing, Hangzhou and Suzhou as the supports. It has made coordinated progress in fields such as scientific and technological innovation, financial services, and high-end manufacturing, creating a world-class urban agglomeration with global influence. The Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area has given full play to the international advantages of Hong Kong and Macao and the manufacturing and innovation advantages of the Pearl River Delta region, strengthened cooperation and exchanges in fields such as finance, trade, science and technology, and shipping, and constructed an open regional collaborative innovation community, facilitating the free and convenient flow of people, logistics, capital, and information within the Greater Bay Area, and promoting the high-quality development of the regional economy.

Regional cooperation has broken down administrative barriers, realized the optimal allocation of resources across regions, avoided vicious competition and redundant construction among regions, improved the overall economic efficiency and development quality of regions, and provided successful examples for the coordinated development of the Chinese economy on a larger scale.

5. Political Behavior Economics: Consolidating the Institutional Foundation and Safeguarding the Long-Term Development of the Economy

5.1. Empowering with institutional strengths and ensuring policy continuity

Under the framework of the socialist political system with Chinese characteristics, democratic centralism runs through the "life cycle" of policies. The top-level economic design at the central level takes shape relying on an efficient decision-making mechanism. With its powerful political authority, it penetrates into the "ends" of local implementation, eliminating persistent problems such as local protectionism and poor implementation of government orders. For regional strategies like the coordinated development of the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region and the construction of the Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area, the central government coordinates the allocation of resources and the division of labor among the three regions of Beijing, Tianjin, and Hebei as well as among multiple cities in the Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao area, breaks administrative barriers, ensures the long-term and stable release of policy dividends, lays a solid foundation for regional economic integration and the free flow of factors, and builds the "cornerstone" of investors' confidence.

5.2. Underpinning risk prevention and control and strictly guarding the bottom line of security

The political operation system has a complete set of risk early warning and response mechanisms embedded in it to safeguard the "fortress" of economic security. When the "dark clouds" of the international financial crisis loomed large, fiscal policy "strengthened efforts and improved effectiveness" by expanding infrastructure construction and stabilizing demand, while monetary policy was "appropriately loosened or tightened" to inject funds into financial institutions in a targeted manner, thus building a solid "firewall" for the financial sector. In terms of food security, we have strictly adhered to the red line of cultivated land, improved the purchasing, storage and adjustment mechanisms to cope with fluctuations in the external food market and ensure food supply stability. In terms of energy security, we have laid out new energy industries such as photovoltaic and wind power, built strategic oil reserves, strengthened energy independence and controllability, and used political "resilience" to buffer external shocks and stabilize the "fundamentals" of the economy.

6. Statesmen behavioral economics: Taking the Helm and Drawing Blueprints.

6.1. Introduction

In the process of economic development of New China, the statesmen played a crucial role in steering the ship, charting blueprints. From the arduous foundation-laying in the early days of the founding of the People's Republic, to the vigorous rise after the reform and opening up, and then to the striding forward of high-quality development in the new era, the eras of Mao Zedong and Zhou Enlai, Deng Xiaoping, and Xi Jinping have each demonstrated unique characteristics. With far-sighted vision, pragmatic and resolute decisions, and persistent promotion, they have written a magnificent history of economic take-off, which is worthy of an in-depth exploration of the logic of statesmen's behavioral economics contained therein.

6.2. The Era of Mao Zedong and Zhou Enlai: Laying the Foundation and Strengthening the Base of Industry and Agriculture

6.2.1 Giving Priority to Heavy Industry and Constructing the Prototype of the Industrial System

At the beginning of the founding of New China, it faced the dilemma of having an extremely weak industrial base and severe external blockades. Leaders such as Mao Zedong resolutely established the strategy of giving priority to the development of heavy industry. Drawing on the experience of the Soviet Union and combining it with China's national conditions, the "First Five-Year Plan" was implemented, concentrating efforts on building 156 key projects covering many fields such as steel (such as Anshan Iron and Steel), machinery manufacturing (Changchun First Automobile Factory), and energy (Fushun Coal Mine, etc.). Premier Zhou Enlai personally presided over the planning and coordination, allocating national resources to fully guarantee the progress of the projects. Although living materials were relatively scarce and construction funds were tight at that time, this strategic choice focused on long-term national defense security and industrial independence, and built the basic framework of the industrial system for China in a short time, giving New China an "industrial backbone", which conformed to statesmen's consideration of strengthening the foundation for national sovereignty independence and economic self-reliance, and drove the initial operation of the economy with the "first move" of heavy industry.

6.2.2. Agricultural collectivization and consolidation of the guarantee of the Economic Foundation

As the foundation of the national economy, agriculture has undergone profound changes in this era. Mao Zedong had an insight into the shortcomings of the scattered, inefficient, and weak-risk-resistant small peasant economy and promoted the process of agricultural cooperation and collectivization. From mutual aid groups to primary cooperatives, advanced cooperatives, and finally, the people's commune system gradually took shape. Farmers were organized on a large scale to build water conservancy projects (such as the heroic feat of the Red Flag Canal), improve soil, and promote agricultural technologies to increase grain production, ensure the supply of industrial raw materials and the food rations of the population, achieve the initial "complementary and mutually promoting" relationship between industry and agriculture, and also supply labor for industry, stabilizing the economic situation under complex internal and external environments, demonstrating statesmen's long-term layout thinking of coordinating the coordinated development of industry and agriculture and consolidating the economic foundation.

6.3. Deng Xiaoping's Era: Reform and Opening-up, Activating the Market and the Vitality of Opening-up

6.3.1. Emancipating the Mind and Breaking the Shackles of Concepts

At the end of the 1970s, the Chinese economy faced development bottlenecks, and the constraints of the old planned economic system became more prominent. Deng Xiaoping, with extraordinary courage and foresight, launched the "Great Discussion on the Criterion of Truth", breaking through the shackles of the "Two Whatevers" and laying the ideological foundation for reform and opening up. In terms of economic concepts, he broke the cognitive limitations of the "binary opposition" between planning and the market, and put forward the view that "it doesn't matter whether the cat is black or white, as long as it catches mice, it is a good cat", emphasizing pragmatic development, clearing the obstacles for introducing the

market mechanism and stimulating the vitality of microeconomic entities, highlighting the crucial role of statesmen in keenly perceiving the current ills and reshaping the ideological orientation to guide economic transformation.

6.3.2. Vitalizing the domestic economy and unlocking market potential

In cities, reforms such as expanding the power and ceding profits of enterprises and the contract management responsibility system were carried out, endowing state-owned enterprises with certain operating autonomy, stimulating enterprises to improve production efficiency and innovate products; vigorously developing township enterprises, absorbing rural surplus labor, breaking the dual industrial barrier between urban and rural areas, and giving birth to diverse market entities. In rural areas, the household contract responsibility system was pioneered. The distribution model of "handing over what is due to the state, keeping enough for the collective, and the rest belongs to oneself" greatly mobilized farmers' enthusiasm for production, released the potential of agricultural production, and turned the vast countryside into an economic "source of vitality", showing the wisdom of statesmen in basing on national conditions and precisely formulating policies to leverage the endogenous power of the market.

6.3.3. Opening up to the outside world and integrating into the world economy

The establishment of special economic zones was the "finishing touch" of opening up to the outside world in the Deng Xiaoping era. Shenzhen, Zhuhai and other places have been transformed from border fishing villages into "experimental fields" at the forefront of opening up. With policies such as tax preferences and trade facilitation, they "attracted" foreign capital, technology and advanced management experience; open coastal cities and open economic zones were gradually expanded, attracting large amounts of overseas investment. China has thus integrated into the division of labor in the world industrial chain, and trade forms such as "processing with supplied materials, assembling with supplied parts, processing with imported materials and compensation trade" have emerged, with a sharp increase in import and export trade volume and accumulation of foreign exchange reserves, irrigating the domestic economic "garden" with the "living water" of external resources and markets, demonstrating the strategic vision of statesmen in breaking through the domestic economic dilemma and expanding the development space through international cooperation.

6.4. The Era of Xi Jinping: High-Quality Development and Implementing the New Development Concept

6.4.1. Innovation-Driven and Overcoming the "Neck-Bottleneck" of Core Technologies

Facing the intensified global scientific and technological competition and the situation of being "controlled by others" in key technologies, General Secretary Xi Jinping has placed innovation at the core of the overall national development. Increasing scientific research investment, laying out "national treasures" such as national laboratories and national research centers, and encouraging universities and enterprises to jointly tackle "neck-bottleneck" problems such as chips, artificial intelligence, and high-end equipment manufacturing; introducing policies to encourage enterprises to improve their independent innovation capabilities, such as

additional deductions for research and development expenses and the STAR Market facilitating the financing of scientific and technological enterprises, giving birth to advantageous innovative industrial clusters such as 5G and high-speed rail, driving high-quality and sustainable economic development with the "innovation engine", conforming to the strategic plan of statesmen to respond to global changes and seize the commanding heights of science and technology and the economy.

6.4.2. Coordinated development and bridging the gap between regions and between urban and rural areas

Great attention is paid to regional coordination and urban-rural integration. The coordinated development of the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region has relieved the non-capital functions and coordinated the industrial layout, and the Xiong'an New Area has risen to become a high-quality urban model; the integration of the Yangtze River Delta has broken administrative barriers, and scientific and technological innovation, finance, and manufacturing have been deeply integrated; the Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area has achieved complementary advantages under the "one country, two systems" and has become a global highland of scientific and technological innovation and the economy. In terms of the relationship between urban and rural areas, the rural revitalization strategy is promoted, increasing investment in rural infrastructure, supporting characteristic agricultural industries, broadening the channels for farmers to increase their income, and building a virtuous cycle of mutual promotion between industry and agriculture and complementary between urban and rural areas, demonstrating the overall thinking of the statesmen in coordinating the overall situation and balancing the development gap.

6.4.3. Green development and achieving a win-win situation for ecology and economy

Adhering to the concept that "lucid waters and lush mountains are invaluable assets", strengthening the legislation and law enforcement of ecological environment protection, strictly controlling high-pollution and high-energy-consuming industries, promoting the green transformation of traditional industries, and widely carrying out ultra-low emission transformation in industries such as steel and chemical engineering; vigorously developing new energy and energy-saving and environmental protection industries, leading the world in installed capacity of photovoltaics and wind power, and starting to explore the carbon trading market, opening up new paths for green economic growth on the premise of ecological improvement, achieving a harmonious coexistence of ecological and economic benefits, showing the development wisdom of statesmen in basing on the long term and taking into account both ecological well-being and economic quality improvement.

6.5. Commonality and Inheritance in the Behavioral Economics of Statesmen

Although Statesmen in different eras have faced different situations, there are significant commonalities among them. They all adhere to the people-centered concept. During the Mao Zedong era, efforts were focused on strengthening the foundation of workers and peasants to ensure people's livelihoods. In the Deng Xiaoping era, reforms were carried out to make the people wealthy. In the Xi Jinping era, high-quality development is pursued to enhance people's well-being.

All of them have made precise judgments based on China's national conditions and the international situation, grasped the pulse of the times to formulate strategies, and these strategies are characterized by coherence and progressiveness. The previous period laid the foundation for the subsequent one, and the latter period inherited and innovated, just like in a marathon relay race, continuously promoting the continuous upgrading of the economy stage by stage.

They also attach great importance to uniting the strength of all parties, bringing together the masses, cadres, intellectuals and others, coordinating domestic and foreign resources to serve economic construction, and using their strong leadership and decision-making abilities to create a joint force for economic take-off.

7. Interpretation of Chinese characteristics from the perspective of institutional economics

Throughout China's economic development process, institutional economics has taken on unique manifestations, with government behavioral economics and party behavioral economics occupying important positions. Unlike traditional Western institutional economics, which emphasizes the spontaneous behavior of market entities and institutional evolution within a given institutional framework, institutional changes and economic development in China are more reflected in proactive planning and active promotion by the Party and the government. As the ruling party, the Communist Party of China has shaped the macro institutional framework and development direction by formulating long-term development strategies and promoting institutional innovation. At the level of formulating and implementing specific policies, the Government has transformed institutional designs into actual driving forces for economic growth through means such as macroeconomic regulation and control, infrastructure construction and the optimization of the business environment. This model of institutional change dominated by the Party and government can concentrate resources more quickly and coordinate the interests of all parties, demonstrating stronger adaptability and flexibility when dealing with complex and changing domestic and international economic situations. For example, when facing a global economic crisis, China has been able to rapidly introduce and effectively implement large-scale economic stimulus plans, while under the framework of Western institutional economics, there are often many institutional obstacles and decision-making dilemmas. The practice of institutional economics with Chinese characteristics shows that the proactive roles played by the Party and the government in institutional design and economic development process can, to some extent, make up for the shortcomings of market failures and spontaneous institutional evolution, and achieve rapid economic growth and structural optimization and transformation.

8. Conclusions

Thus it can be seen that, the origin of institutional economics is fully manifested in the economics of political parties, politicians, governments, and political behavior. In China, institutional economics is characterized by the close interweaving and mutual

complementarity and promotion among the four dimensions of political parties, politicians, governments, and political behavior, continuously generating innovative impetus, efficiently allocating resources, resisting internal and external risks, and building a "moat" for the economic development system. These factors are intertwined and work together to form an economic development model and dynamic mechanism with Chinese characteristics, which has propelled China's economic aggregate to rank second in the world. From the perspective of government behavioral economics, various measures taken by the government, such as macroeconomic regulation and control, infrastructure construction, optimization of the business environment, and competition and cooperation among local governments, have constituted the core driving forces for economic growth. Looking back on the past, the era of Mao Zedong and Zhou Enlai laid the foundation, the era of Deng Xiaoping broke through the situation, the accumulation of Jiang Zemin's era and Hu Jintao's era, and the era of Xi Jinping achieved sublimation. Generation after generation of statesmen, in the journey of economic development, with far-sighted strategies and practical and effective measures, using the principles of statesmen behavioral economics, met the needs of the times and led the Chinese economy from backwardness to glory, with its economic aggregate ranking second in the world. Looking ahead, as long as we adhere to our original aspiration, inherit wisdom, and continue to innovate, we will surely continue to write a glorious chapter on high-quality economic development and contribute more "Chinese solutions" to world economic development.

If we look at the issue from a more comprehensive perspective, the combined financial and economic models of government behavior finance, party behavior finance, party behavior economy, government behavior economy, political behavior economy, politician behavior economy, enterprise behavior economy, tourism behavior economy, agricultural behavior economy and market-oriented economy have achieved success, enabling almost all the poor people in a populous country to get out of poverty and witness the economic take-off. Transport infrastructure projects to rural areas in China can only be completed through national transfer payments. This is part of the economy of party behavior, government behavior, tourism behavior and rural behavior economy.

All in all, behind the take-off of China's economy lies a magnificent epic of the "six-in-one" coordinated and hard-working efforts. Politicians carefully construct guiding ideologies that are in line with the development of the times, thus setting the direction and clarifying the path for progress. Political parties use broad strategies to navigate the giant ship of the economy as it sails through waves and voyages, accurately drawing up blueprints and grasping major trends. The Government was basing itself on the actual situation and endeavouring to formulate precise policies, implementing various measures in detail to lay a solid foundation for development. The stable and excellent political system, like solid armor, escorts the whole process of economic operation, ensuring its stability and order. The vast majority of people work together with great enthusiasm and actively participate, gathering a powerful force for practical work. Coupled with the enterprising spirit that has accumulated and passed down over thousands of years in Chinese civilization, which continuously empowers

efforts, multiple parties have united their strength to jointly play the inspiring melody of the glorious take-off of China's economy.

References

1. 张士海,姚功武.唯物史观视域下毛泽东探索中国式现代化的历史贡献[J].马克思主义与现实,2024,(03):132-139.DOI:10.15894/j.cnki.cn11-3040/a.2024.03.016.
2. 李福岩,卢萍.毛泽东对中国特色社会主义政治经济学的奠基[J].政治经济学研究,2024,(02):60-71.
3. 韩步江.关于毛泽东经济思想的几点思考[J].现代哲学,2024,(03):50-58.
4. 朱慧芳.毛泽东对新中国经济建设的探索[J].中共郑州市委党校学报,2024,(01):57-61.DOI:10.15875/j.cnki.zgzzswdxxb.2024.01.008.
5. 李慎明.正确认识毛泽东领导新中国经济建设的艰辛探索和伟大成就——纪念毛泽东诞辰130周年[J].毛泽东邓小平理论研究,2023,(12):10-32+103.
6. 卢江,黄旭.毛泽东“积累—消费”平衡思想及其当代价值启示——纪念毛泽东同志诞辰130周年[J].当代经济研究,2023,(12):39-47.
7. 赵学军.再论中国共产党的新民主主义经济思想[J].中国经济史研究,2023,(06):137-153.
8. 伍抱一,伍山林.贫富状态演进与经济制度变迁——以中国共产党百年实践为例[J].上海经济研究,2023,(07):118-128.DOI:10.19626/j.cnki.cn31-1163/f.2023.07.008.
9. 张德明.改革开放以来海外当代中国史研究译著评介[J].党史研究与教学,2023,(03):94-106.
10. 张新岩.中国特色贫困治理价值旨归研究[D].吉林大学,2023.DOI:10.27162/d.cnki.gjlin.2023.000509.
11. 陈毅晰.中国共产党财政思想的百年实践与当代启示研究[D].福建师范大学,2023.DOI:10.27019/d.cnki.gfjsu.2023.002458.
12. 胡宗霖.中国共产党推进全民共同富裕研究[D].西安工业大学,2023.DOI:10.27391/d.cnki.gxagu.2023.000078.
13. 高蓉蓉.“一五”计划时期毛泽东工业建设思想及启示[D].华东师范大学,2023.DOI:10.27149/d.cnki.ghdsu.2023.002194.
14. 沈潼.习近平关于加强党对经济工作全面领导的重要论述研究[D].东北师范大学,2023.DOI:10.27011/d.cnki.gdbsu.2023.000881.
15. 罗玉辉.“以人民为中心”:中国特色现代资本市场的逻辑生成与实践理路[J].征信,2023,41(04):16-23.
16. 杨琰.毛泽东经济思想的生成基础、理论内涵与实践成就研究述论[J].毛泽东邓小平理论研究,2023,(01):59-73+107-108.
17. 陈克清.毛泽东经济思想及其当代价值[J].云南大学学报(社会科学版),2022,21(06):18-26.DOI:10.19833/j.cnki.jyu.2022.06.006.
18. 伍山林,周瑞.在发展中追求经济安全——新中国成立以来的演进脉络和总体性分析[J].财经研究,2022,48(11):4-18.DOI:10.16538/j.cnki.jfe.20220715.201.
19. 贺全胜.毛泽东与新中国国民经济恢复和发展[J].湖南行政学院学报,2022,(06):116-126.DOI:10.16480/j.cnki.cn43-1326/c.2022.06.014.
20. 马令坤.中国共产党主要领导人的社会主义经济建设战略思想探析[J].现代商贸工业,2022,43(19):221-223.DOI:10.19311/j.cnki.1672-3198.2022.19.098.
21. 石仲泉.周恩来与国民经济恢复(上)[J].中国延安干部学院学报,2022,15(04):30-

- 40+69.DOI:10.16223/j.cnki.cn61-1456/c.2022.04.005.
22. 关海庭.中国共产党成功启动改革开放原因再分析[J].中共党史研究,2022,(03):137-147.
23. 郭庆振.习近平科技创新思想及其时代价值研究[D].长沙理工大学,2022.DOI:10.26985/d.cnki.gcsjc.2022.000037.
24. 江勇.中国共产党经济伦理思想演进研究[J].道德与文明,2022,(03):165-176.DOI:10.13904/j.cnki.1007-1539.2022.03.013.
25. 杜雨来.习近平新发展理念研究[D].哈尔滨师范大学,2022.DOI:10.27064/d.cnki.ghasu.2022.000009.
26. 庞明川,祝建辉.新时代中国特色社会主义经济规律及其体系研究[J].财经问题研究,2022,(06):16-30.DOI:10.19654/j.cnki.cjwtyj.2022.06.002.
27. 王联稷.习近平关于顶层设计促进经济发展的重要论述研究[D].华南理工大学,2022.DOI:10.27151/d.cnki.ghnl.2022.002637.
28. 韩喜平.中国共产党百年领导经济发展成就与经验启示[J].人民论坛·学术前沿,2021,(11):47-55.DOI:10.16619/j.cnki.rmltxsqy.2021.11.005.
29. 吴正海,范建刚,张占斌.中国共产党百年经济思想与实践[J].西南大学学报(社会科学版),2021,47(04):12-26+227.DOI:10.13718/j.cnki.xdsk.2021.04.002.
30. 谢伏瞻,马建堂,洪银兴,等.中国共产党与中国特色社会主义政治经济学——庆祝中国共产党成立一百周年笔谈[J].经济研究,2021,56(06):4-39.
31. 刘戒骄,孙琴.中国工业化百年回顾与展望:中国共产党的工业化战略[J].China Economist,2021,16(05):2-31.DOI:10.19602/j.chinaeconomist.2021.09.01.
32. 刘佳.新民主主义革命时期中国共产党经济政策及其当代价值[J].山东社会科学,2021,(08):144-148.DOI:10.14112/j.cnki.37-1053/c.2021.08.021.
33. 韩保江.《资本论》对中国共产党经济思想百年演变的影响[J].经济学动态,2021,(07):3-11.
34. 范先佐,李祖民.中国共产党教育经济思想:百年演进、理论自觉与中国特色[J].华中师范大学学报(人文社会科学版),2021,60(04):1-14.
35. 周文,肖玉飞.中国共产党百年经济实践探索与中国奇迹[J].政治经济学评论,2021,12(04):30-50.
36. 刘伟.经济理论与实践的伟大创造——中国共产党推进马克思主义政治经济学中国化的历史进程[J].政治经济学评论,2021,12(04):3-29.
37. 崔友平,刘承礼,赵超,等.百年中国共产党经济思想创新研究[J].经济与管理评论,2021,37(04):5-17.DOI:10.13962/j.cnki.37-1486/f.2021.04.001.
38. 蔡继明,高宏.社会主义基本经济制度再认识的飞跃:从邓小平理论到习近平新时代中国特色社会主义思想[J].政治经济学评论,2024,15(06):19-33.
39. 闪月.邓小平理论的话语研究[D].西南交通大学,2020.DOI:10.27414/d.cnki.gxnju.2020.002529.
40. 刘瑞.习近平经济发展战略观的形成、演变及特色[J].社会科学研究,2021,(02):93-103.
41. 张卓元.邓小平与社会主义市场经济[J].党的文献,2024,(04):52-58.
42. 李源正.邓小平与中国社会主义市场经济的确立[J].党史纵览,2024,(05):14-19.
43. 袁恩桢.江泽民和社会主义市场经济理论[J].毛泽东邓小平理论研究,2011,(03):51-58+84.
44. 本刊编辑部.邓小平、江泽民、胡锦涛关于建立和完善社会主义市场经济体制重要论述摘编[J].党的文献,2009,(01):3-20.
45. 邓水兰,温谄忠.与时俱进的中国特色的经济发展理论——论邓小平、江泽民和胡锦涛对中国经济发展理论的创新[J].南昌大学学报(人文社会科学版),2008,(05):55-60.
46. 张跃腾.区域地方立法协作机制优化研究[D].云南大

- 学,2020.DOI:10.27456/d.cnki.gyndu.2020.002255.
- 47.康佳丰.政府自发合作型区域政策对经济增长的影响研究——基于长三角扩容的证据[J].中国物价,2024,(09):62-66.
- 48.聂鸿天.高质量发展视角下的中国区域经济政策问题研究[D].辽宁大学,2023.DOI:10.27209/d.cnki.glniu.2023.002469.
- 49.康佳丰.政府自发合作型区域政策对经济增长的影响研究——基于长三角扩容的证据[J].中国物价,2024,(09):62-66.
- 50.杨鑫.东莞外向型经济产业集群治理研究[J].商业研究,2010,(05):81-84.DOI:10.13902/j.cnki.syyj.2010.05.026.
- 51.陶东杰,陈政弘,徐阳.营商环境、地方政府税收努力与企业税收遵从[J].广东财经大学学报,2024,39(02):29-43.
- 52.刘志彪,王兵.营商环境、产业转移与区域协调发展[J].河北学刊,2024,44(02):1-13.
- 53.李纯英.国家投资进行农业基础设施建设是增加农民收入的新途径[J].经济问题,2001,(12):41-43.DOI:10.16011/j.cnki.jjwt.2001.12.018.
- 54.李纯英.国家投资进行农业基础设施建设是增加农民收入的新途径[J].经济问题,2001,(12):41-43.DOI:10.16011/j.cnki.jjwt.2001.12.018.
- 55.孙琼雯.交通基础设施建设投资的减贫效应[D].华东交通大学,2020.DOI:10.27147/d.cnki.ghdju.2020.000373.
- 56.薛长深.地方政府投资基础设施建设的资金供给模式研究[J].南方金融,2020,(05):81-89.
- 57.柏菁.新一代信息基础设施建设下的5G赋能[J].广西通信技术,2021,(04):41-45.
- 58.郭鑫.凝心聚力推进新型工业化[N].人民邮电,2024-10-17(007).DOI:10.28659/n.cnki.nrmyd.2024.001821.
- 59.罗威.长沙市政府推进智能制造的问题研究[D].湖南大学,2023.DOI:10.27135/d.cnki.ghudu.2023.003727.
- 60.张萌萌,余明桂.数字政府建设与中小企业投资:来自中小企业融资服务平台建立的证据[J].计量经济学报,2024,4(05):1364-1380.
- 61.胡仁,周凌轲.江苏省人民政府以电子商务物流推动农业农村发展的政策研究[J].物流工程与管理,2022,44(02):64-68.
- 62.杨文银.增强中央政府对国家高速公路网的控制力[C]//中国科协学会学术部.新观点新学说学术沙龙文集 26: 国家高速公路网与经济社会发展关系.人民交通出版社,2009:9.
- 63.陈波.楚雄市高速公路网规划过程中的政府行为研究[D].云南大学,2021.DOI:10.27456/d.cnki.gyndu.2021.000158.
- 64.《国家高速公路网规划》和《农村公路建设规划》内容简介[J].交通运输系统工程与信息,2005,(04):5-7+1-2.DOI:10.16097/j.cnki.1009-6744.2005.04.002.
- 65.重庆规划新增 8 条高铁线路形成 2000 km“米”字型高铁网[J].城市轨道交通研究,2017,20(04):150.
- 66.苏剑.基于总供求模型和中国特色的宏观调控体系[J].经济学家,2017,(07):27-37.DOI:10.16158/j.cnki.51-1312/f.2017.07.004.
- 67.姜长青.改革开放后陈云加强中央经济权威思想研究——兼论经济宏观调控体系的初建[J].江西财经大学学报,2010,(05):97-102.
- 68.毛振华,张英杰,袁海霞.近年来中国宏观调控和经济政策的特征分析[J].中国人民大学学报,2016,30(05):21-28.
- 69.闫建,黄可歆.基于新时代西部大开发新格局的地方政府治理研究[J].行政与法,2021,(07):44-57.

70. 白文杰. 中部崛起战略下的地方政府职能转变[J]. 湖北社会科学, 2008, (12): 77-80.
71. 郭文沛. 东北振兴过程中地方政府执行力研究[D]. 中共吉林省委党校(吉林省行政学院), 2021. DOI: 10.27474/d.cnki.gzjld.2021.000033.
72. 《邓小平文选》第三卷, 人民出版社出版
72. Liu, L. (2023). A New Metrological Theory for Assessing and Grading the Value of International Settlements and Reserve Currencies. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10138301>
73. Liu, L. (2023). Should U.S.-China Relations Be Normalized: A Historical, Religious, and Philosophical Perspective. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13931479>
74. Liu, L. (2024). Huge mistake and irrefutable evidence of awarding the 2024 Nobel Peace Prize to Japan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14196708>
75. Liu, L. (2024). Secrets and irreplicable reasons for the success of the US economic system and model based on historical, philosophical, and logical perspective. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14073758>
76. Liu, L. (2024). Risk avoidance, opportunities, economic development, global governance, peace, Reclassify social systems based on historical and philosophical perspectives. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14186719>
77. Liu, L. (2024). Three main structures of economic behavior in the US: political party behavior economy, politician behavior economy and government behavioral economy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14159700>